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Slip Resistance in Public Buildings: Old Versus New

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KEYWORDS

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Walkway Safety;
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ABSTRACT

Slip and fall injuries are the number one cause of emergency room visits in the United States with a total of more than 10,500,000 visits in 2010. More than 46,000 people died at home or work due to falls in 2022. This study investigated slip resistance (SR) on 10 different flooring surfaces in older vs newer buildings on a university campus in Southwest Montana. The study also compared dry vs wet conditions and found that SR decreased significantly (p -value < 0.01) for both older and newer flooring. The mean scores declined from 0.59 to 0.46 in older buildings and from 0.58 to 0.38 in the newer buildings. Under dry conditions the SR values on all 10 floors were above the 0.50 level indicating high available traction and walkway safety. When wetted, the newer flooring had 13/20 SR values below 0.40 compared to 4/20 for the older flooring and one measurement < 0.30 . This research has developed objective data on the SR in public spaces. Results underscore the need to remain diligent in selecting high-traction flooring and coatings as well as preventing contamination of flooring in public spaces. Every walkway safety program should include management practices such as maintenance methods consistent with manufacturer recommendations, frequent cleaning and rapid spill clean-up when contaminated.

1. INTRODUCTION

Slip and fall injuries are the number one cause of emergency room visits in the United States and caused a total of more than 10,500,000 visits in 2010 (Mills, 2023). The National Safety Council reported that there were 46,653 people that died due to falls at home and work in 2022 (NSC, 2024). At work, in 2017, there were 227,760 falls that were documented, and 887 of those falls caused worker fatality (Archchige et al., 2021). Slips and falls were reported to have represented the first or second highest types of workers compensation claims in most industries in 2009 (DeBusk, Dixon, Gill & Gill, 2019). In 2020, Liberty Mutual Insurance Company reported that falls to lower levels were the third leading cause of nonfatal workplace injuries, which resulted in a cost of more than \$6 billion, and falls on the same level were the second leading cause of nonfatal workplace injuries which had direct costs of nearly \$9 billion (Dixon, DeBusk, Fenley & Gill, 2024). There are many factors that increase the likelihood of a slip and fall event including the surface material, coatings and finish, footwear sole

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design and condition, contaminants present, and human factors (Di Pilla, 2010; Gilkey, 2021; Grieser & Frantz, 2018; Snow et al., 2024; Widas, 2024).

There are two major categories of falls; falls to a lower level (for example, a fall that occurs when a person falls off a roof to the level below) and falls on the same level (when someone slips and loses their balance and control and falls on the walking surface at the same level) (Dixon, DeBusk, Fenley & Gill, 2024). Slips and falls occur when there is loss of balance by a pedestrian because there is not enough friction between the foot and floor. Slippery conditions occur typically when there are contaminants between a shoe and the floor (Brady, 2015; Chang, Leclercq, Lockhart & Haslam, 2016; Gao, 2004; Gilkey, 2021; Snow et al., 2024). The most frequent examples of a contaminant are water, other spilled liquids, snow, ice and some floor finishes (Widas, 2024). There are two types of slips that may occur when walking normally. The most common is when the heel strikes the walkway surface and slides forward on the walkway surface (Abeysekera & Gao, 2001; Di Pilla, 2010; Widas, 2024). The second mechanism is at toe-off, the rear foot can slide backwards when stepping forward (Abeysekera & Gao, 2001; Di Pilla, 2010; Widas, 2024). The probability of either mechanism is increased when a contaminant is present on the walkway surface (Fischer & Fischer n.d.; Gilkey, 2021; Snow, et al, 2024; Widas, 2024).

To identify the causes and prevention strategies of slip and fall incidents the safety professional may use a variety of investigation methods (Chang, Leclercq, Lockhart & Haslam, 2016; Maynard, Di Pilla, Natalizia & Vital, 2012; Troyer, 2012). The Accident Analysis Model is one such approach which consists of five different elements that include: Design, Remove, Guard, Warn, and Train (Fischer & Fischer, 2014). Step one is to evaluate the design of the environment where the incident occurred. It is important to determine the source of the contaminant, to develop and implement design, management, or environmental changes to improve walkway safety. Second, is to remove the contaminant from the environment when design changes are not feasible. Third, is to use guards or barriers to prevent pedestrians from using the walkway. When contaminants have become present such as water or other liquid, you may not always be able to remove the contaminant in a timely manner, in these cases, use guards or barriers to protect the pedestrians from entering a hazardous zone. A good example of an appropriate temporary response is to use tape off barriers and/or cones. Longer term guards might include anti-slip coatings for floors or anti-slip tape for step treads on stairways. Fourth are warnings, when you cannot guard the pedestrian from walkway hazards, you can post or broadcast warnings in the area. Warning signs posted in the environment alert the pedestrians to know that hazards are present so that they can make an informed decision if they should continue walking on the pathway or stop and avoid the risk and take an alternative safer route. A very good example of this approach is the Finnish Meteorological Institute's broadcast alerts when conditions are hazardous for pedestrians (Hippi et al., 2020). The system tracked conditions and found that the greatest risk was when temperatures were near 32 °F. Public health messages included the use of colored signs to alert pedestrians of increasing risk of slip and fall conditions. Messages also encouraged the use of anti-slip devices to be worn on shoes if outside walking was necessary. The system was so successful, it remains in operation today and runs 24/7/365 (Hippi et al., 2020). The final strategy is training, which consists of training people to walk safely, ensuring they know how to navigate dangerous walkway environments. Training could also include choosing appropriate options for footwear that have good slip resistance, how to don snow cleats when it is icy or snowy, and how to avoid slipping. Training can also include how to walk on slippery surfaces, like walking slowly and paying attention (Fischer & Fischer, 2014.).

Another effective strategy to help prevent slips and falls is through good housekeeping and maintenance practices (Gilkey, 2021; Safe Work Australia, 2012). Contaminated floors can cause slips and falls because the surface asperities or roughness is reduced as contaminants layer, fill surface pores or valleys

in the floor surface thereby reducing available traction (Di Pilla, 2010; Kim, 2017). Through regular cleaning and maintenance, contaminants are removed from the floor surface thereby increasing available traction and making a slip and fall event less likely (Di Pilla, 2010). Defective and damaged floors can also cause slips, trips, and falls as well. The presence of cracks, depressions or raised surfaces can cause contaminants to pool or create trip hazards (Di Pilla, 2010; Gilkey, 2021).

There are various types of cleaners that can be used for floor care including alkaline cleaners, acidic cleaners, neutral pH cleaners, and enzymatic cleaners (Di Pilla, 2010; Maynard, DiPilla, Natalizia & Vidal, 2012). It is always best to select the appropriate cleaning agent recommended by the manufacturer of the flooring material. Using the wrong cleaning agent may damage the floor and/or reduce available traction and increase the risk of a slip and fall event. Scheduled cleaning and maintenance are fundamental strategies to ensuring safe walkway conditions (Di Pilla, 2010; NFSI, 2023).

To reduce the risk of slip, trip and fall events to pedestrians at home and work, numerous organizations such as ADA, ANSI, ASTM, ISO, NFSI, NFPA, and OSHA have developed standards and strategies to improve the many aspects of walkway safety (ADA, 2024; ANSI, 2021; ASTM, 2024; Brady, 2015; ISO, 2016; Chang, Leclereq, Lockhart & Haslam, 2016; Di Pilla, 2010; Maynard, Di Pilla, Natalizia and Vidal, 2012; NFSI, 2025; NFPA, 2024; OSHA, 2024). Standards have been developed in the US and internationally. Some organizations create standards and others may only approve and disseminate standards across the world (Di Pilla, 2010). For standards relating directly to SR reference thresholds, ADA, ASTM International, NFPA International, NFSI, OSHA, and were identified (ADA, 2024; ASTM, 2024; NFPA, 2024; NFSI, 2025; OSHA, 2024). Ranges can vary per standard such as high > 0.50 , moderate $< 0.49 - 0.40$, and low < 0.40 SR. Some standards may have up to six categories whereas (Di Pilla, 2010) the NFSI uses three (NFSI, 2024).

While most standards and professionals in the US use SR 0.50 = static coefficient-of-friction (SCOF) as a reference value for safe walkway surfaces, there are no laws that require it or any other value as the minimum SR (Di Pilla, 2010; Leffler, 2009). The National Floor Safety Institute (NFSI) publishes standards for both SCOF and DCOF for both dry and wet walkway surfaces (NFSI, 2025). To estimate the coefficient-of-friction (COF), the safety professional must use a device called a tribometer or slip meter to test the walkway surface (Di Pilla, 2010; Gilkey, 2021).

There are only two devices that have an ASTM F-13 standard for wet testing, which include the portable inclinable articulated strut tribometer (PIAST), and the variable incidence tribometer (VIT) or also known as the English XL. Several studies have verified that the two machines are accurate and reliable for dry and wet testing (Di Pilla & Vidal, 2002). There have been at least 70 different types of tribometers developed over the years that have been identified in scientific journals (Di Pilla, 2001).

In the present study, the English XL VIT was used to test the slip resistance in 10 university buildings on a campus in Southwest Montana. The investigative team planned to evaluate the slip resistance in five buildings with older floor/walkway surfaces (>25 years old) and five buildings with newer floor/walkway surfaces (<15 years). The university was originally built in 1900 and there remains many historic buildings on the campus as well as newer ones that provided a range of flooring materials of varied ages. The campus is a large public space and many people from the community and other places often visit to see various campus attractions such as the famous Mineral Museum or World Mining Museum or just come to watch an athletic competition.

The present study was designed using similar methods described by Sarıışık and Çoşkun (2023). These investigators conducted research on the safety of floor surfaces in public buildings with two portable slip testers. The team selected public buildings including: a hospital, education, police station, courthouse, museum theatre, cinema, social service, library, pharmacy, place of worship, and banking (Sarıışık & Çoşkun, 2023). The researchers found DCOF measure ranging from 0.32 to 0.54 at a university. Overall, they had a wide range of measures with a low of 0.21 to a high of 0.58 derived from testing 30 public buildings (Sarıışık & Çoşkun, 2023).

Another study recently published, evaluated slip resistance on a large university campus in Singapore (Chew, Asmone & Lam, 2024). The researchers used the Pendulum Slip Meter to rank 23 sites and develop a baseline of reliable measures to inform interventions and priority areas. The investigative team set out to develop data for a risk-based approach to walkway safety management at the university (Chew, Asmone & Lam, 2024). Their findings included 386 measurements indicating low to high traction in various locations throughout the university.

Prior research has also been carried out in our laboratory looking at slip resistance of 10 different flooring materials, both wet and dry (Snow et al., 2024). In the study, an intervention was used to improve slip resistance and then retested. Investigators found that using an epoxy coating with asperities greatly improved the slip resistance when wet. Evaluation using the English XL revealed a range of SR values from 0.19 seen on wet flooring uncoated to a high of 0.69 on a wetted tile treated with the anti-slip coating. The current study is a follow-up investigation on our campus.

2. AIMS AND HYPOTHESES

The research aims were to investigate slip resistance in older versus newer floor surfaces, and to investigate slip resistance of dry versus wet conditions in the old and new building.

The hypotheses for the study were:

H01: There is no difference in slip resistance measures between newer versus old floor surfaces.

H02: There is no difference in slip resistance measures between dry versus wet conditions.

3. METHODS

The field investigator achieved competency with the English XL VIT by following the owner's manual with mentoring by the faculty member who was a Certified XL Tribometrist (CXLT). Calibration was defined as +/-0.03 variance from 0.22 which was set by Excel Tribometers. Slip Resistance (SR) readings were initially higher than expected but consistent. The CXLT reached out to Excel Tribometers who provided a new calibration tile, sandpaper for the foot preparation tool, and cleaning brush. The field researcher followed the manual instructions and cleaned the tile with a common dish soap before each calibration and only used distilled water for the calibration and testing. The investigator achieved calibration on a consistent basis using the new tile provided by the manufacturer.

Ten public buildings on the university's campus were identified with assistance from the director of facilities. Five older buildings (>25 years, some > 100 years) and five newer buildings (<15 years, some < 4 years) were selected for evaluation of SR. In each building four zones were identified, based on initial assessment of the buildings including the layout and design and where the most frequently used walkways were. The precise sampling location was marked off in a 6" x 6" square using masking tape. Older and newer flooring surfaces were tested using the English XL Tribometer under dry and wet

conditions. The five older buildings consisted of Main Hall, Chemistry and Biology Building, Science and Engineering Building, Museum Building, and the Mill. The five newer buildings were Natural Resource Research Center, HPER Complex, Student Success Center, the dining hall of the Student Union Building, and the Natural Resources Building.

Sampling was conducted February 20th, 2025 through March 3rd, 2025. Data were collected at a rate of two buildings per day, three to four hours per building, totaling eight hours a day maximum. The strategy in place was to sample two buildings near each other every day. Before and after sampling, the machine was calibrated following the technique provided in the owner's manual (Excel Tribometers, 2016) in compliance with ASTM International standard F 1679-4 (ASTM, 2002).

After the machine was calibrated, the field investigator was able to commence sampling. The sampling technique is similar to the calibration protocol. In each building where the four zones were identified based on walkway use, the precise sampling location was wiped with a clean towel to remove loose debris from the area. Older and newer flooring surfaces were tested using the English XL Tribometer under dry, Figure 1 and wet conditions, Figure 2. Each location was sampled four times in cardinal directions while dry. After each direction, the test foot was prepared, see Figure 3, and the tribometer rotated 90 degrees. Following the dry samples, four wet samples were obtained following the same protocol. In total each building had four locations, each location was tested four times while dry and four times while wet. In addition to sampling SR, water weights were collected before and after each sample.

There were 32 tests performed to estimate the mean SR measurement in each of the 10 buildings totaling 320 samples. At each location the four samples were summed and divided by four for the overall mean. Data were collected using a customized data collection sheet and then transferred to MS Excel for cleaning the data and creation of box plots, and then to Minitab Version 21 for statistical analysis.

Figure 1

Slip resistance assessment of dry flooring with the English XL VIT

Figure 2

Slip resistance assessment of wet flooring with the English XL VIT

Figure 3

Test Foot Preparation for the English XL VIT

The paired T-test was applied to evaluate mean scores for dry vs wet samples from the old buildings as well as in the new buildings. A paired T-test was chosen due to the samples being collected in the same location, just on different floor conditions (wet versus dry). To compare the mean SR scores for the old versus new buildings the Two Sample T-Test was used assuming equal variance. For the equal variance evaluation, the Levene's test was used to ensure that the two populations had the same variance.

4. RESULTS

This research investigated SR measurements in 10 buildings on a university campus. The project required more than 320 SR measurements using the English XL VIT including the calibrations. Each of 10 building floor surfaces were tested in four strategic locations based on walkway use four times each to develop the mean SR estimate. Five floor surfaces in old buildings, all > 25 years and some were > 100 years, had dry SR mean of 0.59 and a range of estimates from 0.52 to 0.62, see Figure 4. The SR measurements were repeated after wetting with distilled water. The wet surface SR mean was 0.46 with a range of estimates lower in most cases from 0.25 to 0.59, see Figure 4.

Figure 4

Old Buildings SR Measures Dry and Wet, Means – Interquartile, Range and Median

Note: Measures > 0.50 are considered high traction, 0.49-0.40 moderate traction and <= 0.39 low traction

The five floor surfaces, when dry, in newer buildings < 15 years had a mean SR of 0.58 and range from 0.53 to 0.64, see Figure 5. The evaluation was repeated after wetting the floor surface with distilled water. The mean was 0.38 with a range of SR estimates with a low of 0.29 to a high of 0.55, see Figure 5.

When comparing dry mean values to wet mean values in the old buildings, they were found to be significantly different with p -value < 0.01, see Table 1. The SR mean estimates were compared for new flooring when dry this measured at 0.58, and when wet it was 0.38, which then revealed a significant difference, p -value < 0.01, see Table 1.

When viewing the distribution of dry SR measures between old vs new buildings, we see varied frequencies in each. All dry walkway surfaces had SR measures > 0.50, see Figure 6. We also observed that many readings were above 0.60. The old and new flooring had 50% of flooring > 0.60, see Figure 6.

Figure 5

New Buildings SR Measures Dry and Wet - Interquartile, Range and Median

Note: Measures > 0.50 are considered high traction, 0.49-0.40 moderate traction and <=0.39 low traction

Table 1

Comparisons of SR Measures in Old and New Buildings Wet vs. Dry

Comparisons	N	Mean	SE Mean	P-Value
Old- Dry	20	0.59	0.009	<0.01
Old- Wet	20	0.46	0.024	
New-Dry	20	0.58	0.007	<0.01
New- Wet	20	0.38	0.014	

Figure 6

SR Measurements in Dry Conditions for both Old and New Buildings - Interquartile, Range and Median

Note: Measures > 0.50 are considered high traction, 0.49-0.40 moderate traction and <=0.39 low traction

When looking at SR measurements in wet condition for old vs new buildings we observed a varied distribution of measures. Testing older flooring revealed 20% of SR measures were > 0.50 compared to new flooring which was seen only in one building. The frequency of SR reduced measures by wetting was similar for old vs new flooring. In the older buildings, there were 7/20 measures and, on new flooring was 6/20 measures between 0.50 and 0.40, see Figure 7.

Figure 7

SR Measurements in Wet Conditions for both Old and New Buildings - Interquartile, Range and Median

Note: Measures > 0.50 are considered high traction, 0.49-0.40 moderate traction and <=0.39 low traction

When looking at the number of SR measures below 0.40 and above 0.30, different patterns were seen. On the old building flooring 4/20 readings were seen whereas in this range. On new flooring 13/20 measures were measured, see Figure 7. Only at a single location in old and new buildings did flooring tests have readings < 0.30, 0.25 and 0.29 respectively.

Comparing dry old flooring to dry new flooring was not significantly different, p-value 0.79, see Table 2. The range for the SCOF was 0.52 to 0.65, see Figure 7.

Table 2

Comparison of SR Measures within Old and New and Dry and Wet

Comparisons	N	Equal Variance P-Value	Mean	SE Mean	P-Value
Dry- Old	20	0.06	0.59	0.009	0.79
Dry- New	20		0.58	0.007	
Wet- Old	20	0.28	0.46	0.024	<0.01
Wet- New	20		0.38	0.014	

The SR scores found while comparing the old versus new on wet flooring had larger variance and was significantly different, p-value < 0.01. The range of the SCOF was 0.25 to 0.63, see Figure 7. In addition to the SR data collection, the floor type and amount of water used when wet sampling was conducted are seen below with SR values for dry and wet flooring, see Table 3.

Table 3

Comparison of SR and water used (oz) on different types of flooring

Type of Flooring	Average SR- Dry	Average SR- Wet	Average water used (oz)
Ceramic/Clay Tile	0.59	0.41	4.82
Concrete	0.57	0.51	3.50
Terrazzo	0.59	0.51	3.65
Synthetic Wood	0.59	0.39	4.55
Wood	0.56	0.30	2.70
Vinyl Tiles	0.58	0.37	3.74

In each building there was a variety of flooring types, there was no statistical analysis carried out on these data. The flooring types with the average slip resistance measures and amount of water used are shown in Table 3. This table shows a range of 0.30 to 0.51 while wet. The average amount of water used was 3.82 oz and ranged from 2.70 oz on wood to 4.82 oz on ceramic and/or clay tiles, see Table 3.

5. DISCUSSION

The present study investigated SR in 10 buildings on a public university campus in Southwest Montana. The aims of the study were to measure, evaluate, and compare SR estimates on older versus newer flooring under dry vs wet conditions. A similar study by Sariisik and Çoşkun (2023) investigated SR in public buildings including six locations on a university campus in a region of Turkey. The researchers used the drag sled (GM 200) and Pendulum type tribometers in their study in contrast to our choice to use the English XL VIT. Their team evaluated 30 different public places to estimate dynamic coefficient of friction (DCOF). The present study used the English XL to derive the SR=SCOF measurements. The DCOF is approximately 70% of the SCOF (Widas, 2024). The present investigation methods were somewhat patterned after the Sariisik and Çoşkun (2023) study.

The researchers on this investigative team also looked carefully at another study by Chew and colleagues (2024) that investigated walkway SR at 23 locations on a large university campus in Singapore. That study was designed to develop objective SR data to be used in ranking risk and prioritization for interventions. The researchers used the Pendulum type tribometer rather than the English XL to assess DCOF (Chew, Asmone and Lam, 2024). Their sampling was conducted both inside buildings and on outside walkways on dry surfaces. Findings revealed SR ranging from high to low DCOF measures using a five-point scale unique to the English Pendulum Tribometer. They tested a variety of flooring and walkways surfaces ranging from tile indoors to outside asphalt and pebbled walkways surfaces. More precisely, investigators found low traction conditions at 47% of locations tested and high traction at 30% of locations tested at the university in Singapore. While the estimated values are different, the conclusions may be similarly compared to understand the overall traction: High, Moderate or Low. Our findings indicated that under dry conditions high traction is noted in all 10 buildings. Most researchers have found that dry conditions, regardless of the walkway flooring surface, provided high available SR (Chang, Lockhart & Haslam, 2016; Di Pilla, 2010; Gao, 2004; Mills, 2024; Snow et al., 2024).

The present study found that dry conditions provided high available traction (SR > 0.50) for safe walking regardless of the age of the flooring surface or type in the 10 buildings. The overall mean SR estimates were 0.58 in the new buildings and 0.59 in the old buildings. We found that 50% of dry older and newer flooring had SR measurements > 0.60, see Figure 7. When compared using the Two Sample T-test, no

significant differences were seen, p-value 0.79. The lowest estimate among all 10 measures was 0.52 and the highest reading was 0.65. Based on US and European standards, the walkways tested would all be considered safe when dry for pedestrian use at work or in the community (ASTM, 2024; ANSI, 2021; NFPA, 2024, NFSI, 2024; OSHA 2024).

Comparatively, Sariisik and Çoşkun (2023) and colleagues found a wider range of DCOF SR on the 30 floor surfaces measured on public spaces from a low of 0.21 in a hospital to a high of 0.58 in a school. Comparing measures at the university, the low as 0.36 to a high of 0.54 DCOF estimates, which should be lower than SCOF readings by approximately 30% and do not provide an exact comparison.

The study completed by Snow et al. (2024) evaluated 10 common indoor walkway surfaces and found high levels of SR on all 10 types of flooring when dry. The dry uncoated flooring tiles had SR estimates ranging from 0.52 to 0.69. So, it appears that most flooring has high traction by all standards under dry conditions. The concern for pedestrian safety arises when the walkway becomes contaminated with water or other liquids (Widas, 2024). Findings revealed significant declines in SR for those uncoated tiles with a range from 0.19 to a high of 0.65. It should be noted that 50% of the flooring tested did maintain high SR > 0.50. These findings correlate nicely with our findings in the current study that all flooring tested dry provided high traction to walkway users and there exists reason to be concerned when walkway surfaces become contaminated with water or other substances that can reduce available traction and walkway safety. We believe that differences when wet are due to the type of flooring material, surface characteristics and coatings or finishes. Further evaluation might have enabled the research team to better understand the reasons for differences in SR values between floor times and locations.

The present study findings revealed that conditions changed when floors were wetted with distilled water, in most cases (30/40), the SR measures declined. Those samples 10/40, that did not decline, were evidence of good SR despite contamination. Again, we believe that differences stem from flooring materials and finishes since we used the same distilled water when testing. Water is the most common contaminant associated with reduced walkway traction (Widas, 2024). In a few cases (2/40), the SR dropped precipitously to a low traction level resulting in an increased risk of slip and fall events for walkway users.

The National Floor Safety Institute classified wet SR measures below 0.30 as low traction and recommended interventions to improve available traction (NFSI, 2024). Interventions could be in the form of applied coatings with asperities to the floor surface enhancing available traction (Snow et al., 2024). The buildings with older flooring had the lowest SR estimate, at 0.25 whereas, the newer flooring had higher SR measures with the lowest estimated at 0.29 yet, the overall means were lower for the newer floors when wet compared to the overall mean of the older flooring, 0.38 and 0.46 respectively. The older buildings had five SR readings between 0.50 and 0.40, very similar to newer buildings with six. The older buildings had only a single test with a measurement below 0.40. Whereas the newer flooring had 13/20 readings between 0.40 and 0.30 and one below 0.30. When compared using the Two Sample T-test, a significant difference was seen, p-value 0.003. These differences may be explained by the newer floor surfaces being made of ceramic and synthetic tiles and wood whereas the older floor surfaces included terrazzo, marble and concrete. Despite the wear associated with older building, they maintained good SR. In one new and one old building, the SR remained the same for both dry and wet. Overall, we found that wet conditions reduce adequate traction for safe walking regardless of the age of the flooring surface on nearly all flooring surfaces in the 10 buildings.

Flooring surfaces fall into six general categories: Stones, concrete, clay, synthetic, ceramic, and woods (NFSI, 2025). Generally, when dry, all types provide necessary available traction for safe walking. However, when contaminated with liquids, traction may be significantly reduced to dangerous levels (Di Pilla, 2010; Gilkey, 2021; Snow et al., 2024; Widas, 2024). Conditions associated with water such as snow, ice and rain may pose challenges to business owners and operators. On the campus investigated, flooring mats are the most common strategy used to reduce water contamination inside buildings. The NFSI (2025) provides standards to help guide owners and occupants on the proper use of floor mats. The NFSI reported that it takes approximately 30' of floor covering to reduce water load by 97% (NFSI, 2025). Mats should also be designed to lay flat with beveled edges and not slide across the walkway surface thereby not creating a trip hazard. The NFSI B101.6 is a standard used as a guide to help commercial facilities in the selection, use and maintenance of floor mats to ensure walkway safety (NFSI, 2021).

Looking at the NFSI standard B1010.0 for the wet surface SCOF guidelines, our wet conditions still showed moderate slip resistance (SCOF 0.40 – 0.59) in most cases, 75% in older buildings but only 35% in newer walkways surfaces met this rating. Again, the likely explanation for our findings are that differences exist in floor materials and finishes and/or coatings applied in general floor maintenance have an impact on the SR under wet conditions. We did not collect information that characterized asperities or types and methods for used by the university for maintaining walkway surfaces. The newer flooring measurements were below 0.40 and considered low traction on 65% of the samples taken, due to the materials and characteristics of the newer flooring.

As shown in Table 3, there was a variety of flooring materials that were sampled, all measurements on dry flooring were considered to have a high slip resistance, ranging from 0.56 to 0.59. When analyzing the wet conditions, there were two types of flooring that demonstrated a high slip resistance both at a 0.51, there was one type of flooring measuring at moderate slip resistance with a 0.41, there were three types of flooring measuring at a low slip resistance at 0.30, 0.37, and 0.39. The amount of water used while sampling can vary greatly based on the person sampling. We did not feel that weight was a good measure of porosity and water absorption. When sampling the investigator put a generous amount of water to ensure coverage of the entire six-inch by six-inch square, whereas the investigator observed others only putting the unbroken film of water in a circle directly under where the test foot strikes.

A limitation was the small sample size; therefore, our findings do not represent other university flooring. This was a convenient sample; our sample of university flooring was not selected randomly. Our data was collected on a small university campus in Southwest MT. Investigators selected 10 buildings, four zones in each and obtained four mean measurements for each zone. Our sample does not represent all buildings on campus or buildings at other universities. Readings may have varied in other areas of buildings that were not sampled. While the English XL was calibrated before and after each test day, there may have been errors in its performance.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it was found that there was a significant difference between wet and dry flooring in both old and new buildings. Our research revealed that the dry floors provide much higher traction than the wet floor. Findings underscore the need for prompt spill clean-up and effective management strategies to keep floors dry. When flooring becomes contaminated with water or other liquids, it must be cleaned up promptly or clearly marked off or barricaded from foot traffic until it can be cleaned up. When comparing the old to new buildings while they were dry, there was a minimal difference between the

two, which demonstrates high traction regardless of age, even when floors are worn down and old they can still retain high slip resistance. When comparing old to new floors while wet there was a significant difference found between the two. The old floors were more slip resistant than the new ones when wet. This is likely due to the type of floor materials and/or coatings applied during maintenance and routine care of floors and walkways. Further testing to evaluate surface asperities was not carried out, use of a profilometer would have aided in characterizing the surface roughness of the flooring. Investigators did not collect data from the university on types of floor maintenance practices or products. Future research should look at these additional factors. This research adds to the literature on SR in public buildings and university campuses.

The takeaway messages are that more tribometry measurement is needed in public spaces to identify higher risk conditions on walkway surfaces so that interventions can be applied. The study also underscores the need for standards to become enforceable law. Slip and fall events cause pain and suffering for victims of injury. The cost in dollars is staggering and needs to be addressed with systematic solutions. More research is needed to evaluate workplace and community walkway surfaces for potential sources of injury and fatality. Future research should include larger sample sizes and the use of multiple types of tribometers. The variability in tribometry readings can be more uniform with correction factors. The development of correction factors should be a priority for standard setting organizations such as ASTM, NFPA, OSHA, and NFSI.

DECLARATIONS

Authors declare no conflicts of interest with the manufacturer or distributor of the English XL VIT. Authors also declare no conflicts with the university regarding floor selection or distribution of results.

Ms. Baylee Bolton was the master's student for this study. She was involved in all phases of the project. Ms. Bolton was the field investigator that collected all samples for this study. Dr. Autenrieth was involved in all phases of the project and provided statistical guidance and manuscript review. Dr. LaDouceur was involved in all phases of the project and served as the out-of-department committee member and manuscript reviewer. His expertise in material science and engineering was value added to the project. Dr. Gilkey was Ms. Bolton's thesis advisor and involved in all phases of the project, including manuscript preparation. He is a CXLT and provided training for competency with the English XL VIT. He is also a Walkway Auditor Certificate Holder from the NFSI.

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